
THE PREFERENCE OF TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ECONOMICS IN OUR COUNTRY

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In this article, the content of the "green" economy is revealed, and conclusions are made about the real possibilities of the transition to the "green" economy. Also, the priorities and advantages of the strategies of the transition to the "green" economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan are highlighted. Recommendations are made for making "green" investments, including creating "green" jobs. At the same time, the role of "green" economy in ensuring the sustainable development of the country will be revealed.

Key words.

Green economy, ecology, investment, strategy, natural resource, sustainable development, green bond

Access

"Green economy" is one of the new and modern directions of the economy that was formed at the end of the last century, it emphasizes the need to reduce the negative impact of human economic activity on the environment, and it is in any case for the environment we can say a direction that calls for fighting with minimal risk. Scientists who study this direction usually consider that it is a component related to the natural environment, which exists in the economy and is considered a necessary part of it.

A green economy is based on green technologies and strategic plans. One of the most promising methods of financing ecological initiatives is attracting socially responsible investments. Its main mechanism, which has a significant potential to reduce environmental damage, is "green investment" in the region, and the importance of the green economy in attracting these investments is significant. In

fact, the issue of attracting investments to the formation of the "green economy" is one of the more complex but very effective ways.

It is known that we understand the green economy as an economy aimed at reducing environmental risks and environmental deficits and sustainable development without damaging the environment. It is closely related to ecological economics, but is applied more politically based on economic knowledge. To be a green economy, the economy must be not only efficient but also fair. Fairness implies the recognition of global and country-level equity dimensions, in particular ensuring a just transition to an environmental economy, and encourages the economical and efficient use of natural resources.

At this point, we can say that "green economy" is reflected differently in the official documents of different countries. For example, among developed countries competition, jobs, in developing countries - sustainable development, solving the problems of poverty, participation of citizens in the economy and equality are defined as issues. However, the most urgent problems in the field of environmental development, first of all, limitations in the field of environmental protection, are not visible in the definitions of "green economy" in any of these documents. This shows that the most important aspect of the green economy is the economy itself and its socio-economic sphere. In the European Community's strategy for the transition to a "green economy" until 2050, it is emphasized that the "green economy" should show a system that integrates ecosystems (natural resources), economy (material resources) and society.

Analysis of literature on the topic

"Green economy" is an economy that improves people's well-being and policies that promote social equity and prevent depletion of environmental and ecological resources while significantly reducing risks.

The increasing commitment by UNEP (and national governments such as the UK) to ideas of natural capital and the idea of full cost accounting under the banner of a "green economy" blurs the distinction between them, and lumps them all together into a "green economy". can redefine as variations of .

Green economy involves the formation of a radically new economy, profitable production and consumption forms and measures aimed at meeting the needs of the population with minimal negative impact on the environment. A "green economy" should ideally bring humanity into a state of balance with nature, in which man gives back to nature as much as he takes from it.

Green economy scientists B.N. Porfiryev, M.V. Sigova, I.K. Klyuchnikov, A.M. Malinin focuses on the strategic, institutional and investment directions of the formation of the "green economy" and the features of the introduction of "green" investments into economic development, the most important aspects of the relationship between the ecological and traditional economy.

Analysis and results

New green and existing jobs emerging as part of the green transition require a trained workforce and provide social inclusion, vocational training, reskilling and cross-sectoral mobility. A green and fair transition requires targeted incentives, structural reforms to improve skills and reduce barriers to employment.

Due to the weather conditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, compared to the countries of Europe and Central Asia, it differs in terms of economic growth due to the high emission of greenhouse gases into the air and the low efficiency of water use. Socio-economic vulnerability is increasing due to severe dependence on natural resources and climate change. The green economy is based on sustainable and efficient use of natural and energy resources, minimizes environmental pollution and greenhouse gas emissions, and increases resistance to natural disasters and climate change. "Green" investments, including the creation of "green" jobs, reducing air pollution, introducing renewable energy sources and modernizing cities, can contribute significantly to the further development of the country's economy.

The process of globalization demands the qualitative renewal of the technological base of the industrialized countries, the transition to a modernized economy to a new technological structure that ensures the improvement of the quality of life and living environment while increasing the level of production efficiency and competitiveness. Abroad, the "green growth" economic policy that makes this transition has been adopted by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) as a strategic direction for the long-term (until 2030) development of all its members.

The government of the Republic of Uzbekistan has set itself the task of increasing the gross domestic product (GDP) per capita from the current 1,700 US dollars to 4,200 US dollars by 2030. International development partners are helping Uzbekistan implement low-carbon development projects, increase climate resilience and reduce the risk of natural disasters. The World Bank supports the transition of Uzbekistan to a "green" economy by developing a long-term strategy of Uzbekistan until 2050 and financing the modernization of agriculture and water

supply systems, introducing renewable energy sources and increasing energy efficiency. will help. The Effective Governance for Economic Development (EGED) program aims to introduce evidence-based approaches and decision-making processes. Small and medium-sized enterprises of the Republic of Uzbekistan are participating in the implementation of the strategy of transition to the "green" economy for 2019-2030 within the framework of the Green Economy Financing Facility (GEFF).

Let's get acquainted with the priorities agreed by the government, which determine the "green" growth strategy and directions of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The priority of sustainable and efficient use of natural resources includes taking measures to support and further develop sustainable agricultural production to achieve food security, conditions of agriculture, rational use of nature and ecotourism. creating enough jobs in the field is an important issue. Also, reducing water consumption and increasing the efficiency of water use, reducing land and forest degradation due to agriculture and livestock grazing are among the urgent issues of this priority direction.

Our next priority is increasing resilience to natural disasters and climate change. The issues of this direction include eliminating the consequences of desertification and climate change on the Aral Sea, improving security systems and strengthening emergency preparedness by improving hydrological, meteorological and climate services, developing natural and technical solutions to increase the resilience of infrastructure to the effects of natural disasters. is to increase the financial resilience of the economy, households and enterprises to dangerous climate events.

One of the priorities defining the "green" growth strategy and directions of the Republic of Uzbekistan is related to innovations and effective "green" investments. In it, the introduction of technical innovation support tools to stimulate "green" growth is considered an important factor, taking advantage of global investments and creating new jobs for the population in the process of transition to a "green" economy are promising plans of this strategy. is studied as

One of the main priorities is the task of further improving the processes of sustainable and inclusive urbanization. In this case, the transition to a more compact structure of cities and conditions of inclusive urbanization, solving problems related to the limited capacity of cities for basic and housing and communal services and improving their quality is one of the important principles

not only of this direction, but of the entire strategy. Support the development of ecological and integrated urban transport to reduce traffic congestion, reduce the number of cars and the demand for parking, and reduce the emission of harmful gases. Preventing urban air pollution to reduce maintenance costs is the development of sustainable tourism along the ancient Silk Road.

The whole world is concerned about climate change, the use of water resources and environmental protection, threatening public health, food security, and economic and social development. These are complex tasks that require increasing the level of international, regional and national cooperation. They also pose significant challenges to policymakers seeking to develop strategies and plans that address the immediate and long-term threats that cause these problems.

"Green economy" means the control and reduction of emissions of pollutants and greenhouse gases, the monitoring and forecasting of climate change, as well as the creation, production and use of energy and resource saving technologies and technologies for renewable energy sources. This includes the creation, production and use of technologies and materials to protect buildings and structures from sudden changes in temperature, humidity and wind load; production of environmentally friendly products, including agricultural (food, natural fibers) and consumer goods (natural and natural-based medicines and personal care products without chemical additives), in other words, "green economy" economy includes the types and results of economic activities that contribute to the improvement of the quality of life and living conditions while modernizing and increasing production efficiency.

Conclusions and suggestions

World experience shows that the "green economy" stimulates regional development, achieving social stability, increasing economic potential through the creation of new jobs in "green economy" sectors. In our opinion, "green investments" are financial instruments such as "green" loans, "green" bonds, "green" insurance, etc., including financial instruments supported by the state, improving the energy efficiency of enterprises, using resources. It allows to direct financial resources and capital flows to reduce the volume of goods, as well as the negative impact on the environment. Many countries are seriously concerned about environmental problems and have developed a complex of economic measures to combat the negative anthropogenic impact.

During the past thirty years of independence and reforms, Uzbekistan has made significant progress in combating the effects of climate change due to

environmental protection and forestry measures in the Aral Sea. Current national plans for the environment and the transition to a "green" economy remain one of the urgent problems of our time. But irrigation and potable water shortages, and reliable electricity supplies remain, as evidenced by recent widespread power outages and unprecedented sand and dust storms. These problems, which negatively affect people, communities, the environment and infrastructure, remind us that much more needs to be done to ensure Uzbekistan's "green" future. The Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Alleviation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the World Bank, the Regional Environmental Center of Central Asia (MOMEM) together with national and international partners organized a series of political dialogues "Transition to a "green" economy in Uzbekistan" developed various reforms.

According to the assessment of the ITKQV of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the results of the strategy of transition to a "green" economy will make a significant contribution to the transition to a "green" economy, climate change, which is vital for the development of Uzbekistan. In January 2022, the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved a new five-year development strategy for 2022-2026. Its priorities include efficient use of energy and resources, reform of the energy sector to reduce fuel consumption and emissions, update the regulatory framework for climate and sectors, promote "green" investments, and use natural resources. investment in optimization and restoration of landscapes.

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